

ECONOMIC FRICTIONS AND FORCES IN FINANCIAL SERVICES**Tolibjonov Xurshidbek***Student of Kokand University**TATU FF student***Yetmishboyev Shaxzodbek***TATU FF student***Azamov Shoxruxmirzo**

Annotation: This article provides detailed information on the role and functions of financial services in the economy, in the activities of companies. The negative and positive consequences of investing in the financial market and the expected future risks of insurance were also discussed. The article also provides information on the network effect and large-scale economy.

Keywords: Payment, investment, financial services, stock exchange, financial intermediaries.

Basically, financial firms, like other firms, are indebted to transaction costs for their existence. In the absence of complete trust between the parties, market interaction on the production and consumer side is characterized by risks, such as underlying agent problems and incomplete or asymmetric data. Addressing them to reduce risk and build trust requires costs for both institutions and consumers, including contracting, searching, and verification costs. For example, lending is characterized by previous asymmetries in the data, as lenders need to determine the risk profile of potential borrowers as they need to monitor the solvency of borrowers. A key feature of payment markets is the need to track payment obligations and verify the identity of account holders or the authenticity of payment tokens. The various participants in the payment processing chain need to make sure that other relationships do not expose them to fraud or liability, and that customers require reliable counterparties to provide funds and reliable processes to deliver them.

Financial market investments and insurance face uncertainty around future outcomes, negative choices, and moral risk. The creators of investment products rely on reliable underwriting and execution services to offer their customers a quality product. Customers, in turn, need to believe in the reliability of investments and transactions based on their ability to buy and sell. As in other areas, the internalization of activities within a single financial services firm overcomes key agent and asymmetric data problems to coordinate interests and track actions. This ensures reliable connections between communities. Linking deposit acceptance to lending allows for closer coordination of asset and liability management. Combining payment making with account management allows the provider to verify the availability of funds until the money transfer instructions are followed. Underwriting, linking sales and sales allows firms to design new investment products according to market conditions and investor preferences.

The presence of uncertainty about future outcomes, such as whether a borrower will go bankrupt, creates additional friction. Because it is difficult to set a contract for all the potential future states of the world - and consequently the solvency status of the borrower - the markets are not fully meaningful. As a result, the allocation of resources may be inefficient: some borrowers have to pay high interest rates to cover the expected (but not necessarily) losses to the lender, expensive insurance may be required, or some loans may not be available at all.

In general, the difficulty of adapting products to the specific conditions of different customers due to asymmetric data or uncertainty in the results means that pricing, maturity, or other conditions will inevitably not fully meet the conditions of some customers. They may reject the offer or the intermediary may find some segments to be commercially unsuitable. However, some customers are not served. Financial services companies are set up to address specific information gaps and frictions associated with intermediation.

Banks are designed to address the issue of maturity changes as depositors are not fully informed about their future liquidity needs. They also cover transaction

costs and risks of intermediary investments between individuals who do not have direct knowledge of other counterparties or who do not have information about economic activities carried out elsewhere. considers management needs. To better manage the uncertainty of the results, banks are diversifying many borrowers. Exchanges and brokers consider the search and transaction costs of individual issuers and investors, reduce data asymmetries by announcing listing requirements and prices, and provide infrastructure and services to facilitate and enable transactions between unfamiliar buyers and sellers. offer. Because much of the intermediation process is not easily visible to customers and the risks can only be realized after a long time, the consumer's need for reliable providers is more pronounced than in other areas.

A provider who has won the trust of customers with a single product can use that trust to offer other services. The provision of these services requires not only information and financial resources, but also real resources. These include labor, equipment, and premises to enter into financial contracts, manage accounts, and process customer transactions. The mix of labor, physical capital, financial capital, and trust capital varies and changes rapidly depending on the type of business. However, the production of financial services is subject to the same frictions that affect production in other sectors to varying degrees, including the indivisibility of real resources and fixed costs. Thus, while financial intermediation is subject to rare data and transactional frictions, as an industry it is also subject to familiar economic forces observed across sectors.

The main economic forces play in the financial and real resources used by financial firms. These include:

Scale economies. On the supply side, traditional financial firms have large fixed investment needs to create and maintain back-office systems and physical distribution networks to connect to the consumer. There may also be minimum capital requirements and fixed costs for compliance operations with regulatory documents. As with any industry with fixed costs, scale economies emerge when a

large manufacturer can depreciate these costs to a larger customer base. The scale also allows for the development of a diversified balance sheet to better manage liquidity and credit risk. Scale reduces the marginal cost of risk and allows for better pricing and / or wider customer service.

- Applied economies. Also on the supply side, financial intermediaries benefit from large-scale economies by combining interconnected financial services that can be delivered through the same physical customer interfaces and use the same balance. Cross-selling of credit products and insurance, as well as offering asset and liability products, can create synergies and reduce costs. Economies of scale are further strengthened by the demand side, as many customers prefer a set of products that are conveniently offered. It also strengthens the institution's role as a gatekeeper to the client.
- Network effects. On the demand side, network effects (or "external parties") are important in financial services such as payments, and as the number of connected users increases, the value of the network to all users (both payers and recipients) increases. A bank that serves businesses, suppliers, and customers can more effectively connect counterparties to make faster payments and provide working capital.

In conclusion, given the existing technology and the rules in place, these forces have historically had advantages over "first movers" and large, vertically and horizontally integrated players. This is especially true for capital-intensive products such as lending, institutions that put consumers' savings at risk, and capital-intensive industries such as deposits and payments. came

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